

Performance of local Indonesian goats fed fermented cocoa pods

Engkus Ainul Yakin^{#1}, Ali Mursyid Wahyu Mulyono^{#1}, Sri Sukaryani^{#1}

[#]*Program Study of Animal Husbandry, Faculty of Agriculture,
Universitas Veteran Bangun Nusantara, Sukoharjo, Indonesia*

Corresponding author : Engkus Ainul Yakin

Abstract— The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of fermented cocoa pod feed on the performance of local Indonesian goats. A total of 25 Bligon goats were used in this study. The experimental design used a completely randomized design with 5 treatments and 5 replications. Treatment T1 = 60% elephant grass + 40% concentrate + 0% fermented cocoa pods, T2 = 60% elephant grass + 40% concentrate + 5% fermented cocoa pods, T3 = 60% elephant grass + 40% concentrate + 10% fermented cocoa pods, T4 = 60% elephant grass + 40% concentrate + 15% fermented cocoa pods and T5 = 60% elephant grass + 40% concentrate + 20% fermented cocoa pods. Feeding 3% of body weight based on dry matter. The variables measured and analyzed in this experiment were feed and nutrient intake ($\text{g head}^{-1} \text{day}^{-1}$), average daily gain ($\text{g head}^{-1} \text{day}^{-1}$), and feed conversion ratio. The results of the study showed that giving 15% fermented cocoa pods combined with elephant grass and concentrate resulted in better dry matter intake ($560 \text{ g head}^{-1} \text{day}^{-1}$), conversion ratio (5.50) and average daily gain (ADG) ($102 \text{ g head}^{-1} \text{day}^{-1}$) compared to other treatments. The conclusion of this study is that fermented cocoa pods up to 15% can provide good results for livestock productivity.

Keywords— cocoa pod, elephant grass, *Phanerochaete chrysosporium*, Indonesian local goat

I. INTRODUCTION

Cocoa pods are a by-product of cocoa plants with a proportion reaching 75% of fresh fruit. Fresh cocoa pods contain high water content so they rot easily. The use of cocoa pods as mulch spread around the plant can become a place for the growth of *Phytophthora palmivora* fungi which cause black pod diseases. This fact causes problems in handling cocoa plant by-products because it can directly reduce cocoa production. One possible alternative is the use of cocoa pods as feed ingredients.

The activity of utilizing cocoa fruit skin is limited by poor nutritional composition, especially low protein content and high lignocellulose components (1). The value of agricultural by-products as feed ingredients can be increased by providing preliminary treatment, either physically, chemically or biologically (2). Preliminary treatment aims to remove, break or reduce the tightness of the bonds between cellulose and hemicellulose with lignin. Lignocellulose bonds can be broken by ligninase such as lignin peroxidase (LiP) and manganese peroxidase (MnP) (3). LiP and MnP enzymes are produced by several organisms including *Phanerochaete chrysosporium*. *P. chrysosporium* in the bioconversion process is able to degrade lignin components first followed by cellulose components (4), has a fast lag phase of around 0-3 days (5), and is able to grow optimally at a temperature of 40°C (6), making it suitable for use in fermentation processes that produce a lot of heat.

Bioconversion with *P. chrysosporium* is able to reduce the tightness of the bond and lignin content which can improve the quality of the cocoa pods. Total digestible nutrient (TDN) and protein content of cocoa pods is almost the same as elephant grass.

Research of this study aims to study usage cocoa pods fermented with *P. chrysosporium* on Indonesian local goat performance.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Cocoa Pod Processing

Fresh cocoa pods were chopped and dried to an estimated dry matter content of 35%. Every 100 kg of dried cocoa pods were placed on a plastic and 100 ppm Mn and 1190 ppm Ca (dry matter basis) were added. The cocoa pods were inoculated with *P. chrysosporium* at 0.9% of the dry matter (7); and mixed thoroughly. The fungus starter culture was grown on the millet for 10 days.

B. Livestock Maintenance

The goats used were 25 local male Bligon goats with an initial body weight of 11.6 ± 1.5 kg. The composition of the experimental goat ration ingredients is shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1.
COMPOSITION OF RESEARCH FEED INGREDIENTS (%)

Material	Treatment				
	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
Elephant grass	60	60	60	60	60
Concentrate	40	40	40	40	40
Cocoa pod fermentation	0	5	10	15	25

The sum is arranged to achieve weight gain 100 g per day, with a protein requirement of 50 g and TDN of 359 g per day⁻¹ (8). Estimated dry matter intake capacity of feed by goats is 645 g per head⁻¹ day⁻¹. The feed that given in the form of elephant grass, fermented cocoa pods and concentrate.

Research is carried out in three periods, namely adaptation, introduction, and data collection. The adaptation period is carried out to adjust the livestock to the experimental environment. The adaptation period is carried out for 30 days, the introduction period is 15 days and the data collection period is 28 days. Feed during the data collection period is given ad libitum, the amount of which is determined based on the consumption of free feed during the introduction period. Drinking water is given ad libitum.

C. Experimental and Data Analysis

The experiment used a completely design with one-way pattern with 5 treatments and 5 replications.

T1= 60% elephant grass + 40% concentrate + 0% fermented cocoa pods

T2= 60% elephant grass + 40% concentrate + 5% fermented cocoa pods

T3= 60% elephant grass + 40% concentrate + 10% fermented cocoa pods

T4= 60% elephant grass + 40% concentrate + 15% fermented cocoa pods

T5= 60% elephant grass + 40% concentrate + 20% fermented cocoa pods

The variables measured and analyzed in this experiment were feed and nutrient intake (g head⁻¹ day⁻¹), average daily gain (g head⁻¹ day⁻¹), dan conversion ratio. Data were analyzed using analysis of variance and testing of the mean value of treatments using Duncan's multiple range test.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Elephant grass is one type of superior grass with a chemical composition that is quite good for ruminant livestock. The use of king grass in rations can be substituted by cocoa pods because they have almost the same protein and TDN content. Fermentation of cocoa pods causes the protein content to be better than elephant grass, while the high lignin content of cocoa pods (38.45%) can be reduced by fermentation to 26.63%. The type of material and the difference in the use of concentrates cause the chemical composition of the treatment rations to vary (Table 2).

A. Feed Intake and Nutrients

Feed intake can be expressed in units of g head⁻¹ day⁻¹ (9), g kg⁻¹ body weight day⁻¹(10), or g kg⁻¹ metabolic body weight (BW)^{0.75} day⁻¹(11). The average of feed intake (Table 3) of dry matter during the study ranged from 434–560 g head⁻¹ day⁻¹ or 60-78 g kg⁻¹ BW^{0.75} day⁻¹. Goat dry matter feed intake reported by several researchers varies, namely 41.5 (12), 54.94 (13), 61.8 (14), and 78.1 g kg⁻¹ BW^{0.75} day⁻¹ (11). Differences in dry matter feed intake are caused by nutrient content, especially protein and energy content of feed (16), physiological status (17), animal sex (18), and feed ingredients in the ration (14). The use of fermented cocoa pods (Table 1) plays a role in increasing the protein content of feed (Table 2) which has implications for increasing dry matter consumption (Table 3), but has not shown any differences.

TABLE 2.
CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF RESEARCH RATION (% DM)

Ingredient components	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
Dry matter	82.30	84.6	85.66	86.3	84.11
Ash	15.13	14.34	13.11	12.14	12.37
Crude protein	10.41	11.80	11.80	12.77	12.02
Crude fiber	27.54	21.91	28.68	23.19	28.50
Crude fat	5.46	9.13	8.77	8.41	4.42
Non-energy extract material	41.45	42.81	37.64	43.49	42.69
TDN*	63.19	68.93	65.25	69.24	63.74
NDF	57.51	54.11	56.69	50.09	57.04
ADF	39.83	32.45	43.06	38.37	44.23
Hemicellulosa	17.68	21.67	13.62	11.73	12.82
Lignin	14.31	12.07	21.27	14.31	16.30
Cellulosa	25.52	20.38	21.79	24.06	27.93

*TDN= 5.31+ (0.412 x % Crude Protein) + (0.249 x % Crude Fiber) + (1.444 x % Crude Fat) + (0.937 x % BETN) (Moran, 2005)

Dry matter intake of treatments T1 and T2 was lower than other treatments. (19) stated that feed intake regulation is an interaction between the characteristics of feed ingredients, rumen and livestock. (20) stated that feed intake can be limited by rumen capacity and the duration of digesta excretion from the rumen. The results of (21) study showed that the specific gravity of elephant grass (0.854 kg/dm^3) is smaller than cocoa pods (1.156 kg/dm^3). Feed materials with a smaller specific gravity indicate more ambu so that they require a larger space in the livestock rumen.

Dry matter intake in the ration ranges from 3.1%-4.0% of body weight. The feed consumed is used for basic life and growth or reproduction. This dry matter intake has met the basic life needs, which are 2.4%-2.8% of body weight (8) but has not been sufficient to increase body weight by $100 \text{ g head}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$. Dry matter requirement to achieve ADG of $100 \text{ g head}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$ of 360 g plus the basic living needs, the amount of which depends on the livestock's body weight (Table 5). Dry matter intake below the livestock's standard needs often occurs because the feed is more resistant to breakdown during chewing, which will reduce the digestibility of dry matter. (19) stated that digestibility is closely related to dry matter intake.

Organic matter intake follows the pattern of dry matter intake. The average organic matter intake during the study ranged from $368\text{-}492 \text{ g head}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$ or $51\text{-}69 \text{ g kg}^{-1} \text{ BW}^{0.75} \text{ day}^{-1}$. Consume these organic ingredients lower than the research results of (9), which was $565 \text{ g head}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$. (22) reported that the consumption of organic matter from cocoa pods in rations by sheep was around $71.8\text{-}95.4 \text{ g kg}^{-1} \text{ BW}^{0.75} \text{ day}^{-1}$. Consumption of organic materials from treatment A is higher low ($P<0.05$) compared to other treatments. Low organic matter intake was caused by dry matter intake ($434 \text{ g head}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$) which is low and the content higher ash (15.13%).

Protein intake intake is closely related to ADG. Protein is used for basic life fulfillment, production, and reproduction. The average protein intake during the study ranged from $45\text{-}72 \text{ g head}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$. Amount protein intake has met the standard estimate of adequate crude protein requirements based on body weight to achieve ADG of $100 \text{ g per day}^{-1}$, namely $56\text{-}58 \text{ g head}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$ (Table 5), except treatment T1. Protein intake treatment T1 was smaller ($P<0.05$) compared to treatments T3, T4 and T5. Low protein intake was caused by the dry matter intake and organic matter (Table 3) and lower protein content (Table 2) compared to other treatments. The use of fermented cocoa pod (treatments T4 and T5) increased the protein content of the ration and feed intake.

The efficiency of nutrient utilization depends on the adequacy of energy and protein. Fulfillment of energy needs is directed at the energy needs for basic life and energy needs for production. Energy intake ranges from $274\text{-}388 \text{ g head}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$. The standard TDN requirement for goats with a body weight of 10 kg and ADG of 100 g is 359 g (8) which is greater than the research results of (11), namely $331 \text{ g head}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$. Energy consumption of T1 treatment was lower ($P<0.05$) than other treatments. In line with other nutrient consumption, low dry matter consumption resulted in low energy intake. The amount of energy intake is a

combination of dry matter intake and energy content of the ration. (23) reported that energy intake increased in line with the increase in energy content of the feed.

Goats require sufficient dietary fiber for normal rumen activity and function. Dietary fiber is degraded by microbes that act as energy providers to support basic life, growth, lactation and reproduction (24). The need for fiber in goat rations has not been clearly established in the guidelines and standards for nutritional requirements. The average of crude fiber intake ranges from 109-157 g head⁻¹ day⁻¹. crude fiber intake in the T2 treatment was the lowest and the T5 treatment was the highest. The difference intake is due to the different crude fiber content and proportion of ration ingredients. The decrease in crude fiber intake in the T1 treatment ration was due to the substitution of some elephant grass with the use of concentrate which has a lower crude fiber content.

The use of fiber as an energy source is closely related to the proportion of fiber components such as cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin. Average NDF intake is 284 g head⁻¹ day⁻¹ or 40 g kg⁻¹ BW^{0.75} day⁻¹. Research conducted by (25) resulted in NDF intake by goats of 32 g kg⁻¹ BW^{0.75} day⁻¹. The NDF content of the ration illustrates the number of components of the cell wall fiber fraction contained in the ration, namely hemicellulose, cellulose and lignin, and this amount in this study is estimated to be too high to support optimum rumen microbial development.

B. Average Daily Gain

Plants are an indicator of the process of nutrient deposition in body tissues. The ability to retain N protein into tissues is influenced by the supply of protein and energy rations. The ADG of goats is 81 g head⁻¹ day⁻¹. This result has not reached the target of 100 g head⁻¹ day⁻¹. This is due to energy intake that is still below standard. Protein intake that has met the needs of goat livestock is not followed by the availability of energy for growth. The initial body weight of livestock before treatment ranged from 12.72-13.88 kg (Table 4) requiring energy ranging from 392-405 g head⁻¹ day⁻¹ (Table 5), while feed energy intake ranges from 274-388 g head⁻¹ day⁻¹ (Table 3).

TABLE 3.
AVERAGE FEED INTAKE OF TREATED GOATS (g head-1 day-1)

Nutrients	Treatment				
	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
Dry matter	434±8	499±59	538±24	560±57	550±21
Organic matter	368±7 ^b	428±51 ^{ab}	467±21 ^{ab}	492±50 ^a	482±16 ^a
Crude protein	45±1 ^b	59±7 ^{ab}	63±3 ^a	72±7 ^a	66±15 ^a
Crude fat	24±0 ^b	46±5 ^a	47±2 ^a	47±5 ^a	24±5 ^b
Crude fiber	120±2 ^{bc}	109±13 ^c	154±7 ^{ab}	130±13 ^{abc}	157±35 ^a
TDN	274±5 ^b	344±41 ^{bc}	351±16 ^{bc}	388±40 ^{bc}	120±2 ^{bc}
NDF	250±2	270±32 ^c	305±14 ^c	281±30 ^{bc}	120±2 ^{bc}
ADF	173±3 ^b	162±19 ^{bc}	232±10 ^{bc}	215±2 ^{bc}	120±2 ^{bc}
Cellulosa	111±2 ^b	102±12 ^b	117±5 ^{bc}	135±14 ^{bc}	153±34 ^{bc}
Hemicellulosa	77±1 ^b	108±13 ^a	73±3 ^{bc}	66±7 ^{bc}	70±16 ^{bc}

Different superscripts in the same row indicate significant differences (P<0.05).

The crude protein and TDN content of the treatment rations (Table 2) the standard requirements. Dry matter intake ranging from 57.95%-75.26% of the requirement (Table 5) is the main cause of low protein and energy intake. Low dry matter intake is caused by high fiber fraction content. (24) explained that ADF content of 18% will produce the highest dry matter intake and decrease at ADF content of more than 18%. Dry matter and non-fiber carbohydrate intake decreases linearly with increasing NDF content of feed (26) because increasing fiber fraction intake will increase chewing activity (24).

T4 account produced the highest ADG, which was 102 g. This result is better from the research results of (22), which was 55 g at a cocoa pod usage level of 30% in the ration. (14) obtained the ADG of goats fed a mixture of several cocoa by-products of 95 g head⁻¹ day⁻¹.

Table 4.
INITIAL BODY WEIGHT, AVERAGE DAILY (ADG), AND FEED CONVERSION RATIO

Nutrients	Treatment				
	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
initial body weight (kg)	13.88±0.58	12.72±1.14	13.50±0.91	13.73±1.06	13.52±3.48
final body weight (kg)	15.53±0.67	14.88±1.29	15.85±0.95	16.58±1.11	15.87±3.57
metabolic body weight (kg)	7.19±0.23	6.73±0.45	7.04±0.36	7.13±0.41	7.02±1.34
ADG (g head ⁻¹ day ⁻¹)	58.95±3.09 ^d	77.38±5.46 ^c	83.93±1.79 ^b	101.79±1.79 ^a	83.93±3.09 ^b
Conversion ration	7.38±0.51 ^a	6.45±0.63 ^{ab}	6.42±0.41 ^{ab}	5.50±0.47 ^b	6.77±1.20 ^{ab}

TABLE 5.
ESTIMATE THE NEED FOR DRY MATTER, CRUDE PROTEIN AND TOTAL DIESTIBLE NUTRIENTS (TDN)
TO ACHIEVE BODY WEIGHT GAIN OF 100 (g per head. ⁻¹ day ⁻¹)

Variable	Treatment				
	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
Needs dry matter	749	716	738	745	738
Needs crude protein					
Metabolic body weight	7.19	6.73	7.04	7.13	7.02
CPm	30	28	29	30	29
CPg	28	28	28	28	28
Needs protein	58	56	58	58	58
Needs energy					
TDNm	203	198	198	201	188
TDNg	202	202	202	202	202
Needs TDN	405	392	400	403	400

CPm = protein requirement for basic life (4.15 g kg⁻¹ body weight^{0.75}); CPg= protein requirement for growth (0.284 g for every g of body weight gain);TDNm= TDN requirement for basic life (28.19 g kg⁻¹body weight^{0.75}); TDNg = TDN requirement for growth (2.02 g for every g of body weight gain) (8)

The use of fermented cocoa pods (T4) gave better results than the use of cocoa pods (T3) and T2. The three ingredients had the same proportion in the ration, but gave different daily ADG, namely 102; 84; and 77 g for treatments T3, T4 and T5, respectively. This was due to better feed intake (Table 4) and chemical composition (Table 2) of the T4 treatment feed. Dry matter intake of the T4 ration was 560 g or 75.26% of the estimated dry matter requirement of 745 g, higher than other treatments. Feed intake that was still below the requirement allowed the substrate to stay longer in the rumen and gave more time for the enzyme to make contact with the substrate.

The greatest loss of dry matter intake especially those from green fodder and agricultural by-products occur in feces (19). The proportion of lost feed and other utilization affects feed efficiency. Feed efficiency can be measured by feed utilization efficiency and feed conversion. Feed conversion is the amount of feed consumed to produce one unit of livestock production (13). A smaller feed conversion value indicates better feed quality. The experimental feed conversion ranged from 5.50 to 7.38. This result is better than the cocoa pod conversion in sheep which ranged from 12.23 to 17.74 (23). (14) research produced a feed conversion of 14.90 in goats fed with sweet potato leaves. The magnitude of the feed conversion value is highly dependent on the digestibility and metabolism of nutrients in the livestock's body. The feed consumed by livestock will be used for basic life and production. Feed conversion of treatment T1 was greater ($P<0.05$) than other treatments. The smallest conversion (5.50) was achieved by treatment T4.

IV. CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this study is that fermented cocoa pods up to 15% can provide good results for livestock productivity. Giving 15% fermented cocoa pods combined with elephant grass and concentrate resulted in dry matter intake (560 g head⁻¹ day⁻¹), conversion ratio (5.50) and ADG (102 g head⁻¹ day⁻¹).

REFERENCES

- [1] Aregheore, EM. Utilization of concentrate supplements containingvaryg levels of copra cake (*Cocos nucifera*) by growing goats fed a basal diet of napier grass (*Pennisetum purple*). *Small Rumin. Res.* 64:87-93. 2006
- [2] Sun, Y. & J. Cheng. Hydrolysis of lignocellulosic materials for ethanol production: a review. *Bioresour. Technol.* 83:1-11. 2002.
- [3] Takano, M., M. Nakamura, A. Nishida, & M. Ishihara. Manganase peroxidase from *Phanerochaete crassa* WD1694. *Bull. FFPRI* 3(1):7-13. 2004.
- [4] de Koker, TH, KK Nakasone, J. Haarhof, HH Burdsall Jr., & BJ H Janse. Phylogenetic relationships of the gentles *Phanerochaete* inferred from the internal transcribed spacer region. *Mycol. Res.* 107: 1032-1040. 2003.
- [5] Shi, J., RR Sharma-Shivappa, & MS Chin. Microbial pretreatment of coJón stalk by submerged cultivation of *Phanerochaete chrysosporium*. *Bioresour. Technol.* 100:4388-4395. 2009.
- [6] Singh, D. & S. Chen. The white-rot fungus *Phanerochaete chrysosporium*: conditions for the production of lignin-degrading enzymes. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 81:399-417. 2008.
- [7] Bonnen, A. M, LH Anton, & AB Orth. Lignin-de-gradeg enzymes of the commercial buJón mushroom, *Agaricuss bisporus*. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 60:960-965. 1994.
- [8] NRC. Nutrient Requirements of Goats: Angora, Dairy, and Meat Goats in Temperate and Tropical Countries. National Academic Press, Washington, DC. 1981.
- [9] van Hao, N. & I. Liden. Performance of growing goats fed *Gliricidia maculata*. *Small Rumin. Res.* 39:113-119. 2011.
- [10] Van Hao, N, & I. Ledin. Tropical foliages : effect of presentation method and species on intake by goat. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 118:1-17. 2005.
- [11] Mandal, AB, SS Paul, GP Mandal, A. Kannan, & NN Pathak. Deriving nutrient requirements of growing Indian goats under tropical conditions. *Small Rumin. Res.* 2005.
- [12] Kondo, M., K. Kita, & H. Yokota. Feeding value to goats of whole-crop oats ensiled with green tea waste. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 113:71-81. 2004.
- [13] Katongole, CB, EN Sabiiti, FB Bareeba, & I. Ledin. Performancee of growing indigenous goat fed diet based on urban market crop wastes. *Trop. Anim. Helath Prod.* 41:329-336. 2009.
- [14] Aregheore, EM. 2006. Utilization of concentrate supplements containingvaryg levels of copra cake (*Cocos nucifera*) by growing goats fed a basal diet of napier grass (*Pennisetum purple*). *Small Rumin. Res.* 64:87-93. 2006.
- [15] Abdou, AR, EY Eid, AM El-Essawy, AM Fayed, HG Hello, & HM El-Shaer. Effect of feeding different sources of energy on performance of goats fed saltbush in Sinai. *J. American Sci.* 7(1):1040-1050. 2011.
- [16] Negesse, T., M. Rodehutsord, & E. Pfeffer. The effect of dietary crude protein levels on intake, growth, protein retention, and utilization of growing male Saanen kids. *Small Rumin. Res.* 39:243-351. 2001.
- [17] Fedele, V., S. Clapsa, R. Rubino, M. Calandrelli, & A.M Pilla. Effects of free-choice and traditional feeding systems on goat feeding behavior and intake. *Livest. Prod. Sci.* 74:19-31. 2002.
- [18] Lewis, R.M. & G.C. Emmans. Feed intake of sheep as affected by body weight, breed, sex, and feed compositon. *J. Anim. Sci.* 88:467-480. 2010.
- [19] Coleman, S.W. & J.E. Moore. Feed quality and animal performance. *Filed Crops Res.* 84:17-29. 2003.
- [20] Yansari, T.A.T, R. Valizadeh, A. Naserian, D.A. Christensen, P. Yu, & F.E. Shahroodi. Effects of alfalfa particles size and specific gravity on chewing activity, digestibility and performance of Holstein dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 87:3912-3924. 2004.
- [21] Toharmat, T., E. Nursasih, R. Nazilah, N. Hotimah, T.Q. Noerzihad, N.A. Sigit, & Y. Retnani. Physical properties high fiber feed and its effect on consumption and digestibility of ration nutrients in goats. *Med. Pet.* 29:146-154. 2006.
- [22] Tuah, A.K, F.Y. Obese, E.R. Orskov, D.B. Okai, D. Adomako, K.O. Amaning, A.N. Said, & J.F.D. Greenhalgh. The performance of Djallonke sheep fed on diets containing various proportions of cocoa pod husk and 5% NaOH-treated maize cobs. *Anim Feed Sci Technol* 5:269-279. 1995.
- [23] Lallo, C.H.O. Feed intake and nitrogen utilization by growing goats fed by-product based diets of different protein and energy levels. *Small Rumin. Res.* 22:193-204. 1996.
- [24] Lu, C.D., J.R. Kawas, & O.G. Mahgoub. Fiber digestion and utilization in goats. *Small Rumin. Res.* 60:45-65. 2005.
- [25] Souza, E.J., A. Guima, Â. MV Batista, K.L. Santosa, J.R. Silva, N.A.P. Moraisa, & A.F. Mustafac. Effects of soybean hulls inclusion on intake, total tract nutrient utilization and ruminal fermentation of goats fed spine-less cactus (*Opuntia ficus-indica* Mill) based diets. *Small Rumin. Res.* 85: 63-69. 2009.
- [26] Zhao, X.H.T., Zhang, M. Xu, & J.H. Yao. Effects of physically effective fiber on chewing activity, ruminal fermentation, and digestibility in goats. *J. Anim. Sci.* 89 : 501-509. 2011.